

OLONITE SURVEY RESPONSE EXTRACT (OSRE)

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Many research have only focused on a single way of collecting data when others are available. This study proposes a template for researchers who intend to use the quantitative means in extracting data for analysis which is called the Olonite Survey Response Extract Template (OSRET)

Keywords: Olonite Survey Response Extract, OSRET, Researcher, Data Collection

Table 1: Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE)

S/n S/a	Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE)
x	Question ¹
	Response xxxx ¹
x	Question ²
	Response xxxx ²
x	Question ³
	Response xxxx ³

Source: Author's Design, 2022

Table 1. shows the Olonite Survey Response Extract (OSRE) as a single entity. This is used to retrieve survey responses which is categorized as a quantitative form. The quantitative in this paper is the primary data. The OSRE is to be used in studies where verbal questions are to be asked and responses written down by the researcher. This is to be used in a single research where the respondents are unable to read nor write or where direct questionnaire filling is not feasible by the respondent. This can also be a phone survey response extract.

Note:

S/n = Serial Number (1, 2, 3, 4 ...)

S/a = Serial Alphabet (a, b, c, d ...). This can also be in capital letters depending on the Researcher's choice.

x = Numerical or alphabetical Numbering of Questions

Question¹⁻³ = Questions asked (Each question that needs a response)

xxxx¹⁻³ = Responses Given (Each response given to the questions asked)

RECOMMENDATION

- i. The Olonite Survey Response Extract Template (OSRET) is recommended for researchers who probably might need to extract information on a question-answer format.